

water rice, submergence tolerant), IR11141-6-1-4 (modern deep water rice variety, elongation ability), IR42 (MV rice), and Lal Dhan (tall traditional rice).

Five 8-wk-old plants of each variety were grown in small (5- × 5-cm) plastic pots. Only the main tillers were maintained. Plants were placed horizontally in trays, and a weight was applied at the uppermost node and a support ventrally under this node (see figure), to stimulate vertical growth of the upper portion of the plant.

Four days after treatment, TCA4, TCA177, Janki, and IR11141-6-1-4 showed excellent kneeling, while IR42 and Lal Dhan were not able to knee, possibly because of the absence of sufficiently developed internodes.

Plants were then submerged for 6 d, initially keeping the leaves partly above the water. IR42 and Lal Dhan had no internode elongation at all, but the other varieties developed two internodes while partially submerged, with the first internode being smaller. TCA4 had the

Sketch of horizontally placed plant, with top part being forced to grow vertically.

longest average total internode elongation of 34.6 cm/plant, followed by TCA177 (32.6 cm). Janki elongated 12.4 cm and IR11141-6-1-4 had 10.4 cm total elongated internodes.

This method has the following advantages: it minimizes the need for

deep flooding to induce elongation, it does not destroy any entry, and it allows scoring (in cm internode length) on a continuous scale between no elongation and very good elongation.

We will evaluate this method for use in elongation genetics work. *JS*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Relation of cross seed set and fertility in rice hybrids

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While breeding for cold tolerance at IRRI, crosses were made with nine japonica and eight indica (including two indica-type derivatives of indica/japonica crosses) cold-tolerant female parents from diverse sources, and six improved plant type, high yielding indica IRRI lines as pollen parents. The cross seeds per panicle and per cross were recorded. Varying degrees of sterility were indicated by seed set of the cross combinations. We tried to find out if the seed set in 102

cross combinations was related to the fertility of the F_1 hybrids.

A total of 299,539 spikelets were emasculated in Feb-Apr 1984 and pollinated using 6 pollinators: 50,864 with IR8866, 48,001 with IR8455-K2, 48,666 with IR15889, 51,439 with IR7167, 48,253 with IR29506, and 52,316 with IR9202. Total seed set was 165,000.

To determine F_1 fertility, 102 hybrids were grown in different environments: in the experimental field, in pots in the greenhouse and in the concrete bed at IRRI, and at CES, Chuncheon, in the 1984 rice growing season. Twenty seedlings of each F_1 were transplanted in single-plant hills, with 25 cm between plants and rows in the field and in the concrete bed, and 5 seedlings in the pots. The main culm panicle of each plant was harvested and placed in a

separate envelope shortly before full maturity to avoid shattering. Spikelet fertility was measured in one panicle per plant, for a maximum of 15 F_1 plants/hybrid combination in Chuncheon, 10 plants in the field and the concrete bed, and 5 plants in pots at IRRI.

The table summarizes the seed set and F_1 fertility data by common indica male parent. The overall mean cross seed set ranged from 53.3% in IR7167 array to 58.8% in IR29506 array with an overall mean of 55.8%. Samgangbyeon and K332 represented the extremes in cross seed set with means of 78.4% and 39.6% among the female parents. Samgangbyeon was followed by Silewah, ARC6000, Shoa-Nan-Tsan, Suweon 287, all indica types. The highest mean F_1 fertility was also recorded in Samgangbyeon (80.2%),

Mean cross seed set and fertility of the F₁ hybrids.

Female parent	Male parent												Mean	
	IR8866		IR8455-K2		IR15889		IR7167		IR29506		IR9202			
	Seed set (%)	Fertility (%)												
<i>Indica group</i> ^a														
Suweon 287 (I/J)	76.4	73.1	61.3	72.5	65.3	81.5	58.5	73.2	65.1	80.3	54.8	73.5	63.6	75.7
Samgangbyeon (I/J)	78.0	79.1	83.1	84.2	80.8	76.7	68.7	79.2	78.6	76.3	81.1	85.6	78.4	80.2
China 988	41.5	85.8	56.6	82.1	56.6	64.9	46.4	66.1	65.8	82.0	62.2	76.9	54.9	76.3
K39-96	56.5	79.9	52.0	73.7	49.7	76.2	43.3	72.8	74.3	95.6	57.7	81.5	55.6	80.0
Leng Kwang	58.1	72.4	48.1	72.2	49.2	69.6	55.3	74.5	61.2	84.2	38.9	69.0	51.8	73.7
Shoa-Nan-Tsan	68.8	81.0	76.2	77.2	64.5	72.9	62.4	73.7	70.2	86.8	54.8	70.4	66.2	77.0
Silewah	72.0	48.3	75.8	38.5	78.8	56.4	74.8	57.0	78.3	56.8	68.6	55.3	74.7	52.1
ARC6000	73.0	61.6	72.9	72.9	72.4	39.4	76.9	87.3	67.6	62.3	72.7	72.7	72.6	66.0
Mean	65.5	72.6	65.7	71.7	64.7	67.2	60.8	73.0	70.1	78.0	61.4	73.1	64.7	72.6
<i>Japonica group</i>														
Suweon 235	45.6	25.5	43.7	43.1	47.3	44.4	45.3	47.1	48.9	53.8	37.8	65.9	44.8	46.6
SR5204-91-4-1	64.3	38.1	56.6	28.7	55.7	46.4	58.9	46.9	64.7	59.1	60.1	60.7	60.1	46.7
SR3044-78-3	46.7	27.0	52.7	34.5	44.7	46.8	40.6	42.7	44.8	53.9	49.3	63.1	46.5	44.7
Barkat	57.1	27.3	58.8	30.0	53.9	32.6	56.0	29.7	48.6	47.1	44.6	49.2	53.2	36.0
K332	43.9	21.7	34.8	18.0	34.3	26.1	39.7	33.3	41.7	43.0	42.9	59.2	39.6	33.6
Shimokita	43.0	38.6	48.8	28.6	41.3	47.8	39.9	37.7	33.9	54.6	46.0	59.5	42.2	44.5
Stejaree 45	42.3	40.6	44.9	24.9	43.2	57.0	43.3	34.6	48.1	55.6	47.7	66.2	44.9	46.5
Anna	33.7	3.7	51.4	18.9	40.4	35.5	38.6	35.5	46.7	47.7	46.7	51.9	42.9	32.2
K84	47.8	48.9	62.3	26.9	61.2	51.2	56.8	45.0	61.6	55.1	46.6	64.3	56.1	48.6
Mean	47.2	30.2	50.4	28.2	46.9	43.1	46.6	39.2	48.8	52.2	46.9	60.0	47.8	42.2
Overall mean	55.8	50.2	57.6	48.6	55.3	54.4	53.3	55.1	58.8	64.4	53.7	66.2	55.8	56.5

^aI/J = indica type derivatives of indica/japonica crosses.

followed by K39-96, Shoa-Nan-Tsan, China 988, and Suweon 287, all indica types. Anna had the lowest mean fertility (32.2%); K332, Barkat, Shimokita, and SR3044-78-3, all japonica types, followed in that order.

The figure shows the relation between cross seed set and F₁ spikelet fertility for the 102 cross combinations. The highly significant and positive association and the scatter of points suggest that japonica/indica cross combinations with a certain range of low seed set also had low F₁ fertility, and indica/indica combinations having a higher range of seed set also produced hybrids with high fertility. Thirteen of the 102 hybrids had approximately normal F₁ fertility (>80%) with K39-96/IR29506 showing 95.6% fertility, but only 3 combinations — Samgangbyeon/IR8455-K2, Samgangbyeon/IR9202, and Samgangbyeon/IR15889 — had more than 80% cross seed set, all in the indica/indica group. The low and

Relation between cross seed set and fertility of F₁ hybrids. IRRI and Korea, 1985.

variable range of seed set in the indica, indica/japonica, and japonica lines in crosses with indica pollinators may have been due to some genetically controlled incompatibility system, depending upon the degree of affinity between the parental varieties used in this study. Such a system has been reported to explain the intervarietal hybrid sterility in rice. *S*

Diversification of cytoplasmic male sterility in rice

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Segregating lines of crosses between varieties of diverse origin were examined for male steriles occurring naturally.

In six of the seven male steriles isolated, sterility was found to be genetic. Cytological studies of these genetic male steriles showed regular meiosis, indicating pollen abortion in postmeiotic stages.

The other male sterile plant isolated from the F₂ of Ratna/Rajai had multiple pistils and whitish rudimentary anthers. This plant was propagated through stubbles and crosses were made. Spikelet fertility in the F₁s showed three classes of F₁ — completely sterile, partially fertile, and fertile — indicating that male sterility is conditioned by cytoplasmic-genetic factors.

Crosses were made with high yielding donors for resistance to disease and stress. In the F₁ hybrids, most varieties had varying fertility restoration ability. Maintainers of sterility were less common. Of the 40 hybrid combinations studied, only IET4699 and Surekha were identified as maintainers. Ratna, Kalinga III (CR237-1), and IET7302 were strong restorers. Utkal Prava (CR1030), Ta-poo-che-ze, and Rasi were weak maintainers.

Backcrosses with IET4699 and Surekha were made to transfer cytoplasmic sterility into their nuclear background. *S*

Heritability of compact panicle and stigma color

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Heritability of compact and lax panicle was examined in the F₁ and F₂ of a cross of Dee-gee-woo-gen (lax) and BU-I (compact).

BU-I is a mutant isolated from X-ray irradiated NC1626. The compact panicles of this mutant have fewer secondary branches and shorter pedicel,

Table 1. Chi-square analysis of F₂ of Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-I for compact panicle. West Bengal, India.

Panicle trait	Frequency	χ^2 ^a	Ratio
Lax	117	1.696	1:2:1
Intermediate	237		
Compact	102		

^ad.f. = 1 at 5% level = 3.841; at 1% level = 6.635.

Table 2. Analysis of F₂ of 4 crosses for stigma color. West Bengal, India.

Cross	Stigma color	Frequency	χ^2 ^a	Ratio
Dee-gee-woo-gen/BJ-1	Black	440	0.349	3:1
	White	155		
Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-3	Black	232	0.068	3:1
	White	80		
IR8/CRM	Black	910	0.444	3:1
	White	290		
IR8/BU-3	Black	256	0.004	3:1
	White	84		
Pooled	Black	1633	0.325	3:1
	White	529		

^ad.f. = 2 at 5% level = 5.991.

resulting in closely attached spikelets. The primary branches also are closely attached with the main axis of the panicle.

The F₁ hybrids had intermediate panicles, resembling the female parent Dee-gee-woo-gen. The F₂ plants showed 3 distinct panicle types: compact (like BU-I); intermediate (like F₁); and lax (like Dee-gee-woo-gen), in a 1:2:1 ratio (Table 1). This indicates that this panicle character is controlled by a partially dominant gene.

To study stigma color, three strains (BJ-1, CRM6-5-90, BU-3) with black stigma and two strains (Dee-gee-woo-gen, IR8) with white stigma were crossed in these combinations: Dee-gee-woo-gen/BJ-1, Dee-gee-woo-gen/BU-3, IR8/CRM-6-5-90, and IR8/BU-3.

In the F₁, all hybrids had black stigma. F₂ plants had black and white stigma in a 3:1 ratio (Table 2). This indicates black stigma is controlled by a single dominant gene independent of apiculus color. *S*

Root systems in hybrid rice

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Chinese scientists reported that strong and active root systems efficiently used applied fertilizers in hybrid rice. We

studied the root system of hybrid rice by the root pulling force method developed at IRRRI. The method assumes a correlation between the force required to pull seedlings or plants and strong, deep root systems which may confer drought tolerance. The results indicated that F₁ hybrids were significantly superior in root pulling force to their parents and check